

The influence of instructional supervision on quality of teaching in public and private primary schools in Luweero town Council, Uganda

Bundi Titus¹, Asimwe Specioza^{1,*}, Mugenyi Edison² and Asimwe Tina³

¹ Graduate School Department of Education, Bugema University, Uganda.

² College of Education, Open, Distance and E-Learning, Kampala International University-Uganda.

³ Department of Education, Nkumba University, Uganda.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 22(03), 313–319

Publication history: Received on 24 April 2024 revised on 01 June 2024; accepted on 03 June 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.22.3.1687>

Abstract

The study was on the influence of instructional supervision on quality of teaching in public and private primary schools in Luweero Town Council, Luweero District, Uganda. The study used descriptive-cross sectional research design and utilized self-administered questionnaire, interview and check list guide. The study indicated a total mean of 3.60 and SD of 0.54 for private primary schools whereas public primary schools had a total mean of 3.82 and SD of 0.48 for instructional supervision and a total mean of 3.35 and SD of 0.49 for private primary schools whereas public primary schools had a total mean of 3.58 and SD of 0.62 for quality teaching. The first hypothesis reject on basis of child centered, discussion and cooperative learning with p value respectively 0.000, 0.002 and 0.000 and was accepted on the basis of demonstration on the basis of p value of 0.390; since t-critical < computed t-value the second null hypotheses was accepted. The study concluded that there is no significant influence of instructional supervision on teaching quality and was reject on basis of checking learner's book, holding model teaching session and post-conference discussion and the null hypothesis was accepted since t-critical < computed t-value was accepted on the basis of lesson observation, checking teachers' professional records and staff appraisal. The researcher made recommended that school administrators should ensure that teachers in their schools use learner centered method of teaching. The government should increase teachers' salaries and provide house allowance for the teachers. Public and private primary schools should benchmark from the performing primary schools around the study area.

Keywords: Instructional; Supervision; Quality; Public; Private; Teaching

1. Introduction

Instructional supervision embraces all activities directed specifically toward the establishment, maintenance, and improvement of the quality of teaching and learning process in schools (Kimeu, Tanui, & Ronoh 2015; Odumbe & Simatwa, 2015; Whye & Asimwe, 2024). Furthermore, it includes improving quality of teaching and learning strategies and providing an atmosphere conducive to teaching and learning. The need for instructional supervision in schools has been voiced by several writers. For example, Kimeu, Tanui, and Ronoh (2015); Odumbe and Simatwa (2015); Apiku and Asimwe (2023); Asimwe and Magunda 2023) observed that "While colleges can do basic training in the arts and skills of teaching, the actual training of teachers must take place in schools where they teach. According to Sagwe, Nyakan, Ngariba (2016) wrote on 'Does quality assurance in school education ensure transparency and accountability?' suggested that if school authorities adopt instructional supervision, such an approach would help the management and the teachers to become aware of their responsibilities with regard to establishing quality in their management and teaching functions.

* Corresponding author: Asimwe Specioza

In 2008, the Ugandan Government established the Directorate of Education Standards to conduct school supervision and to document and share good practices in the education system. Sagwe, Nyakan, Ngariba (2016); Sentubwe, Asiimwe and Oboko (2022) carried out a study in Uganda and reveal that instructional supervision was non-existent in primary schools. Some teachers responded that some of them had been teaching for more than a decade but they had never been supervised by the head teacher in the classroom nor visited by external supervisors. In the same Ngariba (2016) found that the instructional supervision process was not only threatening and stressful to teachers but also judgmental in nature. District inspectors also lack constructive feedback mechanisms to improve teacher practice (MOE, 2016; Apace & Asiimwe, 2023; Whye & Asiimwe, 2024).

In Luweero District, pupils performance in public primary schools in last year's PLE drastically dropped compared to the 1999 results. Of 7,353 pupils who sat for the examinations in the year 2000, only 485 passed in grade A, while in 1999, 640 of 6762 pupils who sat for the exams passed in grade A. The results indicate that the exams were dominated by a few schools in the district. For example, four of the best performing students came from Wobulenzi parent's school, while the fifth came from Lutembe Muslim School. "There was a drop in the general performance last year which can probably be attributed to a general loss of concentration by the teachers on one hand, and a sharp increase in the number of pupils sitting for the examinations on the other (MOE, 2016).

2. Related Literature

Recent research suggests that what the teacher does in the classroom is three times to four times more important in terms of student outcomes than what happens at the whole school level (Enu, Agyonan, Nkun, 2016; Sentubwe, Asiimwe & Oboko, 2022; Apiku & Asiimwe, 2023, Ryatura, Serunjogi & Asiimwe, 2023). However, school supervision practice which would inform staff development for the improvement of teacher practice was still deficient in this regard. A knowledge gap regarding the effectiveness of school supervision practice in staff development remained unfilled. How can school supervision support school improvement through staff development in Primary schools in Luweero district? This is one of the questions this study sought to answer in an effort to fill the knowledge gap.

According to Agyonan, Nkun, (2016) Apiku & Asiimwe (2023) supervision is described as any programme which helps teachers achieve both qualitative and quantitative educational delivery. Supervision is not only meant for the improvement of classroom instructions or lessons. It is equally for the development of the teacher. Agyonan, Nkun, (2016), states that supervision includes, efforts taken by the principal to support teachers and provide resources to facilitate teachers' professional development. Such development and improvement can only be achieved when supervisory system is dedicated to helping teachers to be successful in their classrooms. Kimeu, Tanui, and Ronoh (2015), posit that supervision gives supervisors the hopes of accomplishing improvement in the teachers' classroom instruction. This is showing the effort by the officer, either internal or external, towards seeing an improvement in the general affairs of the schools. These include improvement in the delivery of lessons by teachers, performance of the learners, improvement in school-public relationship and general administration of the school. Such efforts would go a long way in the promotion of quality education as teachers would feel motivated to put in their best towards the realization of educational goals.

The study by, Kimeu, Tanui, and Ronoh (2015); Odumbe and Simatwa (2015); Apiku and Asiimwe (2023); Asiimwe and Magunda (2023); Asiimwe and Zuena (2023); Maila and Asiimwe (2024) examined the contribution of supervision to school development in education particularly focusing on head teachers' views on the value and practice of reporting on teacher performance in Primary schools. The inspectors made a grading of each observed teacher and gave feedback to the teacher. The inspectors also gave verbal reports regarding the observed teachers' performance to the head teacher. A total of 305 head teachers participated in the study through filling a questionnaire. The participants ranged from those who thought supervision had no value for school improvement to those who were overwhelmingly positive about its contribution to school improvement. The researchers conducted postal questionnaire surveys and 21 telephone interviews in Primary schools which had been inspected in the first, second and fourth years of the supervision cycle.

The findings of the study revealed that there were problems in reporting on staff performance using the prevailing supervision procedures given the widespread discrepancies between the inspectors' grading of teachers and the schools' judgment about the same teachers. The respondents expressed lack of confidence in the inspectors' judgments of teacher performance especially in cases where teachers that head teachers had rated highly were graded low by the inspectors and vice-versa. The value of post-supervision reports to the schools could not be over-emphasized especially if the reports highlight areas of strengths and weaknesses plus areas that need improvement.

Kimeu, Tanui, and Ronoh (2015); Odumbe and Simatwa (2015); Apiku and Asiimwe (2023); Asiimwe and Magunda (2023); Asiimwe and Zuena (2023); Maila and Asiimwe (2024) carried out a study to investigate the effectiveness of the MOES inspectorate department in supervising private Primary schools in selected private schools in Kampala District. The study assessed the role of the inspectorate in ensuring that private Primary schools have adequate structures and facilities, and in ensuring that the teachers' terms and conditions of service in private Primary schools were favourable (MOE, 2016). The study employed the cross sectional survey research design with questionnaires and interviews to collect qualitative and quantitative data. The findings of the study indicated that the inspectorate was not adequately supervising private Primary schools and that the supervision process was not attuned to educational expectations and reforms.

The teachers in private schools were found to be working under unfavorable and stringent terms and conditions, which impeded their performance. This study focused on supervision for policy and compliance to minimum standards of Primary school management and not the improvement of teacher practice and head teachers practice. The findings indicated that the supervision process had some deficiencies. The research gap regarding the contribution of school supervision practice toward school improvement through staff development still stood. The study by Kimeu, Tanui, and Ronoh (2015); Odumbe and Simatwa (2015); Apiku and Asiimwe (2023); Asiimwe and Magunda (2023); Asiimwe and Zuena (2023); Maila and Asiimwe (2024) did not address that gap.

A study by Sagwe, Nyakan, Ngariba (2016) was conducted to analyze the manner in which instructional supervision was conducted and the behaviour responsible for the sustenance of quality educational provision for teachers in the war-affected schools in Paico sub-county in Uganda. A total of 89 respondents took part in the study including 68 teachers, 15 head teachers, one inspector, one principal inspector and one district education officer. The participating teachers and head teachers represented 15 primary schools. The study employed the qualitative design and data was collected from teachers, head teachers and inspectors through questionnaires and interview schedules. The findings of the study revealed that the war situation in the district had negatively impacted on both the teaching environment and the conduct of supervision, supervision was neither focused on individual teachers nor was it related to classroom observation, there was a need for concerted efforts on the part of all stakeholders to nurture and sustain teacher morale and commitment.

The findings of the study cast yet another dark shadow over the school supervision process in Uganda. The post-war situation notwithstanding, the study revealed that the conduct of school supervision was deficient in terms of improving teacher practice. The fact that the supervision process did not focus at all on the dynamics of teacher practice in the classroom undermined any expectations for classroom improvement. A research gap concerning how school supervision practice must support school improvement through quality of teaching remained unfilled. One question remained unanswered: how can school supervision support school improvement through quality of teaching in Primary schools in Luweero district? Therefore, this study investigated the effectiveness of school supervision in quality of teaching in Primary schools in Luweero district in Uganda.

3. Methodology and discussion

This study was based on a descriptive and cross sectional research design. Descriptive type of research involves quantitative and qualitative and was used because much information were needed to find data that is rich in insight, understanding, explanation and depth of information that can be justified statistically. Descriptive design was used because it describes the phenomenon at the time of the study. Cross-sectional design was used because the researcher seeks information from heterogeneous respondents (that is to say, different respondents with different characteristics).

3.1. Influence of Instructional Supervision on Quality of Teaching in Public and Private Primary Schools

The study was to establish the influence of instructional supervision on quality of teaching in public and private primary schools in Luweero town Council, Uganda. This was analyzed using linear regression to examine the influence of each instructional supervision on quality of teaching in public and private primary schools in Luweero town Council, Uganda of which the results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Influence of Instructional Supervision on Quality of Teaching in Public and Private Primary Schools

Coefficients ^a					
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	
	(Constant)	4.444	4.108		0.282
	Checking Learner's Book	1.410	0.306	0.295	0.000
	Lesson Observation	0.269	0.217	0.075	0.218
	Checking Teachers' Professional Records	0.401	0.316	0.107	0.207
	Staff Appraisal	0.089	0.177	0.047	0.615
	Holding Model Teaching Session	0.674	0.216	0.194	0.002
	Post-conference Discussion	0.839	0.119	0.467	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Teaching Quality

Sources: Primary Data N =114

In the multiple regression results in Table 8 Beta values and significance values or p – value are used to establish the influence of instructional supervision on quality of teaching in public and private primary schools in Luweero town Council, Uganda.

It establishes that checking learner's book demonstration obtained a Beta value of 0.295 or 29 % with a p – value of 0.000. Implying that, there is much influence of checking learner's book on teaching quality in primary and private primary schools. The findings suggest that checking learner's book was given much attention. Moreover, lesson observation indicator did not influence teaching quality with a Beta value 0.075 or 07.5 % with a p – value of 0.207 which is higher than the significant value of 0.05 implying that lesson observation is not much implemented in the study area. In addition, checking teachers' professional record as shown with a Beta value of 0.107 or 10.7 % with a p – value of 0.207 which implies that p value was high than significant value which is 0.05 meaning that checking teacher's professional records is not implemented much in the study area.

Furthermore, the results in Table 8 revealed that staff appraisal obtained a Beta value of 0.047 or 4.7 % with a p – value of 0.615 implying that there was insignificance influence of staff appraisal on quality teaching in public and private primary schools in the study area. This implies that staff appraisal has negligible influence on quality of teaching in both private and public primary schools. This leading the researcher to reject the first hypothesis on the basis of staff appraisal.

When it came to holding model teaching session, the findings holding model teaching session obtained a Beta value of 0.194 or 19.4% with a p – value of 0.002 implying that there a significant influence of holding model teaching session on quality of teaching in the study area. Lastly, the results revealed that post-conference discussion had a Beta value of 0.467 with a p – value of 0.000 implying that post-conference discussion had a significant relationship with quality of teaching in the study area. This may imply also that the first hypothesis which said that there is no significant influence of instructional supervision on teaching quality was rejected on basis of checking learner's book, holding model teaching session and post-conference discussion with p value respectively 0.000, 0.002 and 0.000 and was accepted on the basis of lesson observation, checking teachers' professional records and staff appraisal with a p-value respective of 0.218, 0.27 and 0.615.

During the interview with the head teachers and the director of studies, majority of them raised confirmed that there was clear link between early coverage of the syllabus affect the performance in national examination for instance some of them had to say that:

"It helps the learners to do enough revision thus they perform well, it helps the learners to acquire enough knowledge to answer questions at the exams, it gives the teachers much time to do revision and revisit some challenging topics."

The findings implies that head teachers feels that when the syllabus is fully covered, students might not be able to finish the program and might lead to poor quality of teaching in both public and private primary schools. Therefore, covering the syllabus on time will lead to high quality of teaching in both public and private primary schools in the study area.

The findings is in agreement with the literature where it was suggested that what the teacher does in the classroom is three times to four times more important in terms of student outcomes than what happens at the whole school level (Usman, 2015; Wanjiru, 2015; Mwangi, 2015; Kayindu & Asiimwe, 2020). However, school supervision practice which would inform staff development for the improvement of teacher practice was still deficient in this regard.

The findings is in line with the literature of Kimeu, Tanui, and Ronoh (2015); Odumbe and Simatwa (2015); Apiku and Asiimwe (2023); Asiimwe and Magunda (2023); Asiimwe and Zuena (2023); Maila and Asiimwe (2024) examined the contribution of supervision to school development in England particularly focusing on head teachers' views on the value and practice of reporting on teacher performance in Primary schools. The inspectors made a grading of each observed teacher and gave feedback to the teacher. The inspectors also gave verbal reports regarding the observed teachers' performance to the head teacher. A total of 305 head teachers participated in the study through filling a questionnaire. The participants ranged from those who thought supervision had no value for school improvement to those who were overwhelmingly positive about its contribution to school improvement. The researchers conducted postal questionnaire surveys and 21 telephone interviews in Primary schools which had been inspected in the first, second and fourth years of the supervision cycle.

The findings was in line with the literature of Kimeu, Tanui, and Ronoh (2015); Odumbe and Simatwa (2015); Apiku and Asiimwe (2023); Asiimwe and Magunda (2023); Asiimwe and Zuena (2023); Maila and Asiimwe (2024) carried out a study to investigate the effectiveness of the MOES inspectorate department in supervising private Primary schools in selected private schools in Kampala District. The study assessed the role of the inspectorate in ensuring that private Primary schools have adequate structures and facilities, and in ensuring that the teachers' terms and conditions of service in private Primary schools were favorable.

The findings is in agreement with the literature where it was documented by Agyonan, Nkun, 2016; Apiku & Asiimwe, 2023, Ryatura, Serunjogi & Asiimwe, 2023) which was conducted to analyses the manner in which instructional supervision was conducted and the behaviour responsible for the sustenance of quality educational provision for teachers in the war-affected schools in Paico sub-county in Uganda.

4. Conclusions

The study was concluded that there is no significant influence of instructional supervision on teaching quality was reject on basis of checking learner's book, holding model teaching session and post-conference discussion and was accepted on the basis of lesson observation, checking teachers' professional records and staff appraisal. The null hypothesis was accepted since $t\text{-critical} < \text{computed } t\text{-value}$. The implication of the findings to the statement of the problem is that there must have been improvement on the instructional supervision in the study are which brought an improvement on the quality of teaching. The findings has an implication on the theoretical framework in fulfilling the functions of instructional supervision which are administrative, educational and supportive. Since instructional supervision is implemented at high level, quality of teaching was also high as one of instructional supervision function.

Recommendations

Based on the research findings, the researcher made the following recommendations in line with the stated objectives, the government primary and private primary schools should improve on providing enough instructional materials. The school administrators should ensure that teachers in their schools use learner centered method of teaching. The government should increase teachers' salaries and provide house allowance for the teachers. Public and private primary schools should benchmark from the performing primary schools around the study area.

Compliance with ethical considerations

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

Sponsorship

This article was sponsored by the authors themselves

References

- [1] Apiku, C. and Asiiimwe (2023), Association, of school, classroom environment factors and academic performance of girls in Mathematics in public primary schools in Gombe District, Wakiso, International journal of multidisciplinary, research and growth evaluation, Issue4, Vol, 4
- [2] Asiiimwe, S. &Magunda, H. 2024 Revisiting behaviourism, cognitivist, constructivism and teaching adult learners.
- [3] Asiiimwe, S, Zuwena, H. The influence of head teachers' management practices on teachers' motivation in selected public secondary schools in Nyagatare District, Rwanda (JARIIE-ISSN(O)-2395 4396 Vol-9 Issue-1 2023.
- [4] Chuk, M. Asiiimwe, S. Asiiimwe. T. 2023. Factors influencing implementation of Free Secondary Education in Government Schools: A Case of Schools in Maswa District Simiyu Region
- [5] Tanzania, ISSN (online): 2582-7138, Impact Factor: 5.307 (SJIF) Volume: 04, Issue: 06
- [6] November-December 2023. DEO (2016). District Education Officer, Luweero District.
- [7] Dey, A. Choudhury, M. M., Mollah, S., Kim, M.H. (2015). Evaluation of teaching methods on students' academic Performance in the University of Dhaka, AEIJMR – Vol 3 – Issue 4 – April 2015 ISSN - 2348 - 6724 1 www.aeph.in
- [8] Enu, J., Agyman, K. O, Nkum, D. (2015) Factors Influencing Students' Mathematics Performance In Some Selected Colleges Of Education In Ghana, International Journal Of Education Learning And Development Vol.3, No.3, Pp.68-74, April 2015, Published By European Centre For Research Training And Development UK.
- [9] Kayindu, V. Asiiimwe, S. (2020). Extra- Curricular Activities as Predictors of Primary Pupils' Academic Self-Efficacy in Kira Municipality, Wakiso District. IJRISS 4 (1): 7, (2020).
- [10] Kimeu, R. M., Tanui, E., Ronoh, A. (2015) Influence of Instructional Resources on Primary School Students 'Academic Performance in Makeni County, Kenya, International Journal of Scientific Research and Innovative Technology Vol. 2 No. 1; January 2015
- [11] Kothari, C. R. (2011). Research Methodology, Methods and Techniques. New Age International Publisher, New Delhi, India.
- [12] Maila, S.J & Asiiimwe, S. 2024. Relationship between participatory management and teachers' job commitment in public secondary in Ibindo Division, Kwimba District, ISSN (online): 2582-7138, Impact Factor: 5.307 (SJIF) Volume: 05 Issue: 01 January-February 2024
- [13] Ministry of Education (2010). Central Province KCSE-2010 examination results analysis. Nairobi: Ministry of Education.
- [14] Mugenyi, E. Matagi, L. Kobusingye, L. Asiiimwe. S. 2023. Family factors, school environment and conduct problems among primary school pupils in Kampala District, Uganda, ISSN (online): 2582-7138, Impact Factor: 5.307 (SJIF) , Volume: 04, Issue: 04, July-August 2023
- [15] Mwangi, M. P. (2015). Administrative Factors Influencing Students Performance in Kenya Certificate of Primary Education in Public Day Primary Schools in Thika West District, Kenya. Master's Thesis, University of Nairobi
- [16] Odumbe A. G., Simatwa, E. M.W. & Ayodo T.M.O. (2015). Factors Influencing Student Academic Performance in Day-Primary Schools in Kenya. A Case Study of Migori Sub county. Greener Journal of Educational Research ISSN: 2276-7789 ICV: 6.05 Vol. 5 (3), pp. 078-097, July 2015. (DOI <http://doi.org/10.15580/GJER.2015.3.071815099>)
- [17] Ryatura, J. Serunjogi, C.D, Asiiimwe, S. 2023. Competency-Based Teaching Approaches and Student-Teachers' Academic Performance in Public Grade A Teachers' Colleges in Lake- Zone, Tanzania, International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews, Vol 4, no 11, pp 563-574 November 2023
- [18] Sagwe, G. M., Nyakan, P. O. & Ngariba, S. M. (2016). Influence of Curriculum Delivery on students 'Academic Performance in KCSE in Public Primary Schools in Nyamira South Sub County. International Journal of Novel

Research in Education and Learning Vol. 3, Issue 2, March - April 2016, ISSN 2394-9686 (www.noveltyjournals.com)

- [19] Sentubwe, F. Asimwe, S. Oboko, M. (2022). Relationship between Instructional Resource Availability and Students' Academic Performance in Biology at Advanced Level in Buikwe District, Vol. 7, Issue 2 Dec, 2022, 53-65
- [20] Usman, Y. (2015). The Impact of Instructional Supervision on Academic Performance of Primary School Students in Nasarawa State, Nigeria Journal of Education and Practice ISSN 2222-1735 (Paper) ISSN 2222-288X (Online) Vol.6, No.10, 2015 (www.iiste.org)
- [21] Wanjiru, N. L. (2015). School Based Factors Influencing Head Teachers' Instructional Supervision Practices in Public Primary Schools in Kiambu County, Kenya. Master's thesis, University of Nairobi
- [22] Weyhe, B. Asimwe, S (2024), Examining the access, Quality and Relevance gaps in Liberia's Educational Policy Environment, International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research E-ISSN;2582-2160, Volume 6. Issue, 3, May-June, 2-24.